

STUDIES ON EFFECT OF SEED BIOPRIMING WITH MPKV BACTERIAL CONSORTIUM ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF PIGEONPEA (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) millsp.)

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted to study the inoculation effect of seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium on growth, nutrient uptake and yield of pigeonpea at College of Agriculture, Pune. The results of the present investigation revealed that among the different biopriming treatments, seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 75% RDF was found to be the most effective as it recorded significantly the highest germination (95.77%), plant height (127.80 cm and 144.0 cm), root length (37.67 cm and 45.70 cm), dry weight of shoot (16.88 g plant⁻¹ and 20.03 g plant⁻¹) and dry weight of root (4.13 g plant⁻¹ and 5.92 g plant⁻¹) at flowering and harvest stage of the crop, number of nodules (33.27 plant⁻¹), number of pods (112.67 plant⁻¹), 1000 seed weight (95.47 g), seed yield (20.31 q ha⁻¹), NPK uptake (120.43, 13.71 and 90.84 kg ha⁻¹, respectively) and population of Rhizobium, PSB and KMB (33.05, 23.67 and 23.22 x 10⁶cfu g⁻¹ soil, respectively) at flowering stage of pigeonpea, however it was statistically at par with the treatment of seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 100% RDF for growth parameters, microbial population, nutrient uptake and seed yield of pigeonpea. From the present investigation it can be concluded that seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 75% RDF was found to be the most beneficial for getting higher seed yield of pigeonpea with 25% saving of nitrogen and phosphorus dose of chemical fertilizers to pigeonpea.

Keywords: MPKV Bacterial consortium, Rhizobium, PSB, KMB, Pigeonpea, seed biopriming**Introduction**

The pigeonpea, or *Cajanus cajan* (L.) millsp, is a major rainfed and semiarid food grain legume crop that is grown all over the world. With an area of 5.41 million hectares and an annual production of 4.49 million tonnes, India alone provides 72% of the area and 66% of the global pigeonpea production (FAO, 2016). Among dietary legumes, pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) millsp.) is an essential source of vitamins, minerals, and protein. They also play a vital role in human nutrition. The pigeonpea is the second most principal pulse crop in India and the fifth most significant grain legume crop globally (Pratibha *et al.*, 2015). Known by many as red gram, tur or arhar, the Indian subcontinent alone provides over 92% of the world's total pigeonpea production (Khanumet *et al.* 2015 and Reddy *et al.* 2016).

By soaking the seeds in liquid bacterial culture solution for a predetermined amount of time, a technique known as "seed biopriming" starts physiological processes within the seed and prevents plumule and radicle emergence before the seed is sown (Bisen *et al.*, 2015). According to (Sukanya *et al.* 2018), bio-priming is a seed treatment or coating method that uses advantageous PGPR under regulated hydration circumstances to enhance pre-germination techniques without causing the radicle to emerge. It is connected to increased plant growth and resistance to biotic and abiotic stressors, including elevated activity of hydrolytic enzymes and reactive oxygen species (ROS), detoxifying activity of enzymes, changes in internal plant hormone levels and differential gene expression in plants. (Deshmukh *et al.*, 2020).

According to the study by (Santner *et al.*, 2009) microbes can help induce plant growth by secreting substances that improve seed germination and root growth, including auxins, abscisic acid,

gibberellic acid, cytokines, and ethylene. A novel seed treatment method called "biopriming" combines physiological and biological methods to enhance growth of the plant and manage illness. It's been utilised recently as a substitute technique to manage numerous soil- and seed-borne infections. Because it combines the application of a beneficial microbe on the seed surface with seed hydration, it is therefore regarded as a sophisticated strategy for treating seeds (Singh *et al.*, 2016).

Material and method

The present investigation was carried out during Kharif 2023 on the field of Biological Nitrogen Fixation Scheme and Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture Pune.

Seeds

The seeds of Pigeonpea variety ICPL-87 used for the experiment were obtained from the Division of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, Pune

Collection of bacterial consortium

The required MPKV bacterial consortium and reference strain of *Pseudomonas* was collected from the Department of Plant Pathology and Agril. Microbiology, MPKV, Rahuri.

Biopriming of seed with bacterial consortium

Then 25 g of each bacterial consortium and reference strain of *Pseudomonas* was taken into beaker separately and made up the volume to 1000 ml. by adding water. The pigeonpea seeds were soaked in the solution of bacterial consortium and reference strain separately for 12 hours before sowing. Then seeds were taken out from solution and kept for drying for 30 min in shade. Then sowing of the experiment was carried out in the field.

Treatment details

Treatment No.	Treatment details
T1	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing +100% RDF
T2	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing +75% RDF
T3	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing +50% RDF
T4	Seed biopriming with reference strain of <i>Pseudomonas</i> @25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing +100% RDF
T5	Seed biopriming with reference strain of <i>Pseudomonas</i> @25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing +75% RDF
T6	Seed biopriming with reference strain of <i>Pseudomonas</i> @25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing +50% RDF
T7	Untreated control

Observations recorded

Seed germination percentage (%), shoot length (cm) and root length (cm) was taken. Moreover, the plant growth observations viz. plant height and root length at flowering and harvesting stage, no. of nodules plant⁻¹, no. of branches plant⁻¹, no. of pods plant⁻¹, 1000 seed weight, seed yield and microbial population was recorded.

Results and discussion

The present investigation was conducted to study the inoculation effect of seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium on growth, yield and nutrient uptake of pigeonpea. The results of the present investigation revealed that among the different biopriming treatments, seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 75% RDF was found to be the most effective as it recorded significantly highest germination (95.77%), plant height (127.80 cm and 144.0 cm) and root length (37.67 cm and 45.70 cm), at flowering and harvest stage of the crop, number of nodules (33.27 plant⁻¹), number of pods (112.67 plant⁻¹), 1000 seed weight (95.47 g) and seed yield (20.31 q ha⁻¹), however it was statistically at par with the treatment of seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 100% RDF for growth parameters and seed yield of pigeonpea. Thus, these treatments were found to be significantly superior over rest of the treatments in ameliorating growth parameters and seed yield of pigeonpea (Table 1).

Moreover, seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 75% RDF was found to be the most effective as it recorded significantly highest population of *Rhizobium*, PSB and KMB (33.05, 23.67 and 23.22 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, respectively) at flowering stage of pigeonpea and was found statistically at par with the treatment of seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 100% RDF for microbial population of *Rhizobium*, PSB and KMB (30.77, 22.37 and 20.96 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil, respectively) (Table 2).

The results of the present investigation are in line with those of Bansal (2009), Qureshi *et al.* (2011), Argaw (2012), Tarafder *et al.* (2016) and Shete *et al.* (2019), who reported that seed inoculation of *Rhizobium*, PGPR and PSB alone or in combination resulted in increased plant height, root length, no. of nodules and seed yield in various legume crops. Furthermore, Ghadge and Murumkar (2020) found that, when compared to an uninoculated control, soybean plant height, root length, no. of nodules and seed yield was increased following seed inoculation with a consortium of *Rhizobium*, PSB and KMB. Moreover, the results of the present investigations are in agreement with the results of Cao *et al.* (2016) who reported that the application of rhizobial inoculant and/or PSB inoculant to soybean significantly increased the population of *Rhizobium* and PSB at flowering stage of soybean. Furthermore, Shete *et al.* (2019) reported that inoculation of mungbean seed with *Rhizobium*, PSB and KMB contributed to the increase in their population at flowering stages of crops and the counts were higher in inoculated treatments compared to uninoculated control. Results of the present investigation are in conformity with the results of these scientists.

Conclusion

Among the different inoculation treatments, seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 75% RDF was found to be the most effective as it recorded significantly highest germination, shoot length, root length, dry matter production, nutrient uptake, microbial population and seed yield of pigeonpea. From the present investigation it can be concluded that seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium + 75% RDF was found to be the most beneficial for getting higher seed yield of pigeonpea with 25% saving of nitrogen and phosphorus dose of chemical fertilizers to pigeonpea.

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Table. 1 Effect of seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium on seed germination, plant height and root length at flowering and harvest stage, no. of nodules plant⁻¹, no. of pods plant⁻¹, 1000 seed weight and seed yield of pigeonpea.

Tr. No.	Treatment details	Germination (%)	Plant height (cm)		Root length (cm)		Average number of nodules plant ⁻¹	Average number of pods plant ⁻¹	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield (q ha ⁻¹)
			Flowering	Harvest	Flowering	Harvest				
T ₁	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 100% RDF	93.27	124.60	142.20	35.83	43.73	32.02	108.80	93.97	19.48
T ₂	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 75% RDF	95.77	127.80	144.00	37.67	45.70	33.27	112.67	95.47	20.31
T ₃	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 50% RDF	91.94	122.20	141.53	33.87	40.43	29.27	107.33	91.33	18.10
T ₄	Seed biopriming with reference strain @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 100% RDF	89.66	120.53	139.67	30.63	38.77	27.20	104.47	86.80	17.65
T ₅	Seed biopriming with reference strain @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 75% RDF	90.22	121.07	140.53	31.60	39.43	28.47	106.53	90.00	17.89
T ₆	Seed biopriming with reference strain @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 50% RDF	87.58	119.40	138.13	26.73	37.27	26.60	101.87	84.87	16.67
T ₇	Untreated control	84.25	115.73	135.07	24.40	34.57	20.53	89.83	81.47	15.55
	S.E(m)±	0.85	1.11	0.69	0.60	0.73	0.45	1.47	0.56	0.60
	CD at 5%	2.62	3.36	2.10	1.85	2.26	1.39	4.53	1.74	1.88

Table.2 Effect of seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium on microbial population of *Rhizobium*, PSB And KMB at flowering stage of pigeon pea.

Tr. No.	Treatment details	Microbial population at flowering (x10 ⁶)		
		<i>Rhizobium</i>	PSB	KMB
T ₁	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 100% RDF	30.77	22.37	20.96
T ₂	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 75% RDF	33.05	23.67	23.22
T ₃	Seed biopriming with MPKV bacterial consortium @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12hrs. before sowing + 50% RDF	22.40	20.30	17.99
T ₄	Seed biopriming with reference strain @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing + 100% RDF	15.85	17.50	16.43
T ₅	Seed biopriming with reference strain @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing + 75% RDF	18.83	18.83	17.50
T ₆	Seed biopriming with reference strain @ 25g kg ⁻¹ seed in 1 litre water for 12 hrs. before sowing + 50% RDF	12.40	16.43	13.04
T ₇	Untreated control	9.59	12.04	11.31
	S.E(m)±	0.92	0.46	0.95
	CD at 5%	2.82	1.41	2.94
	Initial	0	9.54	10.33